

VOIDS CHARACTERISATION IN CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

Increased use is being made of advanced composite materials for the critical structure of both civilian and military aircraft. Such materials often have a higher strength-to-weight ratio compared to conventional materials, are corrosion resistant and are able to be tailored to meet specific mechanical criteria [1]. Problems can arise during the manufacture and handling of these materials due to their non-homogeneous nature, which result in defects, some of which can be hidden or uncharacterised [1]. Void content/porosity, delamination, matrix cracks and impact damage are just some of the composite material defects. These defects need to be identified and characterised for determination of the 'quality' of a composite structure, as these parameters have a significant effect on the mechanical properties of the material and can act as failure initiation points [2]. Conventional composite void characterisation techniques provide results of limited accuracy and/or reliability due to inherent testing errors. Such techniques include:

- (1) Archimedes test, for which the samples actual density is calculated using the Archimedes principle. Then, the void volume fraction is calculated using the theoretical density of the sample with no voids present [3]. The technique relies on accurate knowledge of the fibre and matrix density and weight fraction values of the laminate. The method can give a negative void fraction, which is theoretically impossible [4].
- (2) Matrix burn-off, which utilises a furnace to degrade and remove the matrix from around the fibres, facilitating measurement of the fibre weight fraction. Archimedes density testing is initially required to measure the samples actual density [3], with accurate knowledge of the constituent densities still required to calculate

the samples void volume fraction. Fibre degradation and convection currents affect the accuracy of this technique, because fibre mass can be degraded or removed. This error is especially prevalent for carbon fibre reinforced composite (CFRC) laminates, because the temperatures reached when achieving matrix burn are above carbon fibre oxidation [5].

- (3) Matrix digestion, a method that is similar to Matrix burn-off, except that acid is used to digest and remove the matrix from around the fibres instead of using thermal degradation. Toxic fumes are produced during the chemical break down of the matrix [6], rendering this process messy and dangerous.
- (4) Microscopy, which is a visual and destructive analysis technique that allows the void size, shape and distribution to be analysed [7]. The method is widely used in industry due to its visual characterisation advantage, but also has an inherent section-bias error associated with analysing two dimensional (2D) cross-sections of the sample.

The above-mentioned conventional void analysis techniques are limited in their accuracy and reliability, and also have limitations regarding extraction of information from their data. The first three techniques, which are non-visual, give only total void fraction and cannot analyse individual void size, shape and distribution. Microscopy can detect this important visual information, but it is limited by the information being 2D and not representative of the whole sample.

X-ray Computed Tomography is a novel non-destructive and visual technique that can be used for three dimensional (3D) analysis of internal structures. The technique has been used for about 5 decades, predominately for medical diagnosis [1].

Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT), a more recent development, allows for wider application, including the qualitative and quantitative non-destructive evaluation of composite materials [1]. The technique is based on recording the change in attenuation along the path of an X-ray beam fired through a sample [8]. This allows a cross-sectional image to be reconstructed mathematically from attenuation measurements made at different angles by the detectors. Because the thickness of each 2D slice is known, the images can be stacked virtually to create a 3D model. Binary conversion (black and white) of the image then allows the voids to be separated from the fibre and matrix, which make up the laminate.

The objectives of this study are a comparison of the Archimedes technique and microscopy with micro-CT for analysis of voids in CFRP materials.

2 Experimental Procedures

Two 24-ply oven cured carbon fibre reinforced thermoset plastic (epoxy) (CFRP) laminates were manufactured. One panel was made from unidirectional (UD) preimpregnated (preg) carbon fibre, while the other was a twill weave carbon fibre prepreg. Oven curing of the laminates under vacuum was used to ensure that voids were present. Samples of size 15 x 7 x 5 mm were cut from the middle of the panels for testing. This size was a compromise between requirements of the different techniques, with micro-CT requiring small samples to reduce data file size. Carbon fibre/epoxy laminates were used for the samples due to the particular interest in characterisation of this material.

The determination of the void volume fraction using the Archimedes Theoretical versus Actual Density technique was carried out in accordance with ASTM D3171. The samples were smaller than the recommended testing standard volume of 1cm³, due to size restrictions of the micro-CT technique. This is assumed to have negligible impact on the accuracy of the Archimedes test results.

The void volume fraction (V_v) is given by equation 1, in terms of the mass fraction ($\%_m$) and density (ρ) of the primary constituents

$$V_v = 100 - \rho_{sample} \left(\frac{\%_m \text{ matrix}}{\rho_{matrix}} + \frac{\%_m \text{ fibre}}{\rho_{fibre}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The material properties must be accurately known, because minor variations can significantly affect the calculated void volume fraction. Using Archimedes principle, the actual density (ρ_{sample}) of the sample is determined, with the sample first being weighed in air and then while submerged in water. These steps should be carried out accurately, with no air bubbles present on the sample surface while submerged.

An Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy (ESEM) microscope was used for the microscopy analysis due to its superior contrast and digital imaging capabilities compared to that of an optical microscope. The technique is destructive, because a sample cross-section is required. The testing preparation required for microscopy analysis of composite materials is time consuming and sometimes difficult, due to the non-homogenous composition of composites. The sample is set in resin after which a flat cross-section is prepared to a mirror-like finish, with no visible preparation damage, such as scratches and void distortion. Sequential grinding of the surface with smaller sized particle paper, from 35 to 2.5 microns, achieves a high quality surface finish. The process is difficult, because the brittle fibres regularly break free and gouge large scratches in the specimen surface. The finished surface should have few or no scratches, because these appear as voids when using image analysis software.

Image analysis software is used to process the microscopy images. Analysis is undertaken of the individual pixels that make up the image cross-section. The process requires the microscopy cross-section image to be converted to binary form, with the voids remaining black and the matter (fibre and matrix) converted to white. The image is then 'cleaned', to remove unwanted noise and outliers. The image is then analysed using built-in tools, giving the total number of voids, their overall area fraction, as well as individual void size, shape and 2D location.

The micro-CT scanning and image reconstruction requires little specimen preparation, because the technique is non-destructive. The scanning, image reconstruction and the data acquisition processes can

be time consuming. These processes depend on sample size and the micro-CT scan settings, especially the scanning resolution. For this study, a constant scanning resolution of 7 microns was used for each sample, this representing the physical size of the voxels (3D pixels) comprising the image slices. The data acquisition software used was provided by the manufacturer of the micro-CT scanner. It gives overall void fraction and the individual void size, shape and distribution in three dimensions. It is also capable of producing 3D rendered models of the voids.

3 Results and Discussion

The Archimedes theoretical versus actual density testing technique is a non-destructive and non-visual technique, which gives the overall void volume fraction within a specimen. Because the technique is non-visual, the total void volume fraction of the sample is the only quantitative data obtained. The technique requires accurate knowledge of the densities and mass fractions of the material constituents, this being an inherent disadvantage of the method, limiting its application. Small variations of densities or mass fractions can lead to variations in the results, with the potential to generate a negative (and impossible) void fraction.

The material properties, fibre and matrix density, of both laminates for this study were acquired from the carbon fibre prepreg manufacturer. The exact matrix density is unknown due to cure variables; consequently a range between 1.15-1.18 g/cm³ was given by the manufacturer. Hence, a probable void volume fraction was calculated from Equation 1. The pre-cure weight fraction values were acquired from the material data sheets produced for each batch of prepreg material, with the final values taking into consideration the resin bleed during cure.

In spite of the limitation of needing knowledge of material properties, the Archimedes Theoretical versus Actual Density technique is more suitable than other techniques in some situations, because visual information is not required, at least initially. An example application of this technique is the inspection of autoclaved cure products for manufacturing defects, such as bag rupture and corner bridging. Such manufacturing defects typically cause significant increases in the overall

void volume fraction. Hence, if the material properties and constituent volume fractions are known with reasonable accuracy, these faults can be identified using this technique. Further investigation can follow, or the specimen can be discarded.

Using microscopy analysis, the complete cross-section can be produced in multiple images, which can be meshed together to create a complete cross-sectional image at a sufficient 100x magnification (Figure 1).

2mm

Fig.1. A unidirectional laminate cross-section comprised of 21 individual ESEM images.

Microscopy analysis allows important individual void characteristics to be assessed, as shown in Figure 2, for example.

Fig.2. Projected area distribution of individual voids with respect to count and area fraction from microscopy analysis, and with respect to sphericity from micro-CT analysis.

The microscopy analysis results in Figure 2 show that $\approx 45\%$ of the total number of voids with a projected area diameter between 15-200 microns in Figure 1, have a projected area diameter of less than 50 microns, while only accounting for $\approx 6\%$ of the total void area fraction. Also, these results indicate that voids, with a projected area diameter greater than or equal to 200 microns, account for only 1.5% of the total number of voids greater than 15 microns. However, they contribute to $\approx 24\%$ of the overall void area fraction. This example demonstrates the benefits of visual analysis, from which the individual characteristics of the voids are evaluated against each other.

Figure 1 shows that the voids within a laminate are inconsistent, with variable shape and location. Due to this variability, microscopy characterisation of composite laminates has an inherent section bias. Specifically, one cross-section is not necessarily an accurate representation of the complete sample. To limit the effects of section-bias in this study, three cross-sections per sample were analysed. This, however, is time consuming.

For the micro-CT scanning reconstruction, the parameters were kept constant for all samples, although the alignment parameter was tailored for increased accuracy. The current micro-CT technology is limited to scanning of small samples only. Small increases in the sample size and scanning resolution significantly increases the required scanning time, data file size and the required data acquisition computer power. For this study, the samples required a scanning time of one hour at a scanning resolution of 7 microns. This produced a file size of 10 gigabytes.

Micro-CT analysis has the advantage of being capable of viewing a 3D-rendered model of the internal structure of a sample (Figure 3). Three dimensional visual analysis of the internal laminate structure provides the user with a basic understanding of the laminate. Large elongated voids are apparent in Figure 3, with the small rounder voids being scattered throughout the volume. This non-analytical understanding of the voids present within the sample can be used to help direct the analytical analysis.

Fig.3. A 3D micro-CT rendered model of a unidirectional laminate.

The software provided with micro-CT facilitates 3D analysis of micro-CT scans. The operation of the software is similar manner to that for microscopy, although it also incorporates the through-slice thickness of the pixels and the interconnectivity of the voids between cross-sectional images.

Figure 2 shows the average sphericity of individual voids with respect to their projected area diameter for the unidirectional laminate sample from analytical micro-CT analysis. A linear decrease in sphericity, as the projected area diameter increases, is depicted. This indicates that voids become more elongated as void volume increases, a trend that matches the non-analytical visual observations made from the 3D rendered images in Figure 3. The agreement highlights the effectiveness of non-analytical visual analysis. Analytical micro-CT analysis is capable of giving the overall volumetric void fraction and the total number of voids, while also giving the 3D size and location of individual voids.

The accuracy and reliability of the void characterisation techniques, tested within this study, are discussed in the following paragraph. It is not possible to comment on the accuracy of each method, as the actual void content is unknown. Rather, a comparative variation is assessed. The void volume fraction results are obtained from testing five samples per technique. Due to section-bias errors, three cross-sections per sample were analysed using microscopy, making a total of fifteen.

Fig.4. Calculated void volume fraction by Archimedes, microscopy and micro-CT analysis.

In Figure 4, the average calculated void volume fraction and standard deviation of the five unidirectional laminate samples tested using each of the analysed techniques, are shown. The average void volume fraction among the three techniques is between 1 and 2 per cent. This variation is minimal in the context of the whole specimen volume and the inherent errors of each technique. However, the small discrepancy between the void characterisation techniques is significant for high end products, such as in the aerospace industry. A notable difference between the techniques is the larger standard deviation for the void fraction obtained using the Archimedes method. This standard deviation (0.74%) is nearly twice that obtained by microscopy (0.41%) and over three times that obtained using micro-CT (0.23%).

Regarding the individual void characterisation results obtained by microscopy and micro-CT, the data show similar trends. For example, both techniques show that the majority of voids account for a small minority of the total void fraction. Also, as void volume increases the void becomes increasingly elongated. Although the trends are similar, the microscopy results feature a predominately higher standard deviation, which can be attributed to that technique's inherent section-bias. This highlights the variability and potential inaccuracy of microscopy.

The techniques investigated all feature limitations and accuracy constraints. For example, microscopy is a destructive technique, micro-CT currently requires a small sample size, and Archimedes

Theoretical versus Actual Density requires accurate knowledge of the physical properties and constituent mass fractions of the materials. The Archimedes technique is shown to have a relatively large standard deviation. It also is incapable of giving characteristic data about individual voids. Although microscopy is able to measure this critical information, its accuracy and reliability is limited due to the errors of section-bias. Micro-CT is reliable, and features a low standard deviation and adequate void characterisation tools. The current limitations of micro-CT analysis, in particular the small sample size, are due to limitations of technology and are not inherent within the technique.

4 Conclusion

The accuracy and reliability of void characterisation techniques for composite materials are assessed in this study. Each technique is shown to have particular strengths and weaknesses, with Archimedes and microscopy having critical inherent limitations. Considering the required preparation and testing processes, the characterisation information available, cost and the overall accuracy and reliability, it is concluded that micro-CT analysis is the most accurate and reliable technique for characterising voids in composite materials.

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